

Analytical coding scheme for identifying and analysing academic definitions in CLIL writing

This Zenodo record contains an analytical coding scheme for the analysis of academic definitions in CLIL and other related contexts (EMI, ESP). The coding scheme is a methodological research instrument derived from peer-reviewed research (see <https://doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2020.1798868>) and is made openly available here to support transparency, replication, and reuse.

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1. Purpose and scope of the coding scheme

This document presents a reusable analytical coding scheme designed to identify and analyse academic definitions in students' written disciplinary texts. The scheme is intended for research in Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), English-medium instruction (EMI), and English for Specific Purposes (ESP) contexts, with a particular focus on disciplinary literacy development.

The coding scheme operationalises “defining” as a cognitive discourse function realised through one or more clauses that specify the meaning of a target term (definiendum). It enables systematic analysis of both the structural composition and the functional-semantic resources used in definitions, independently of language accuracy or surface correctness.

This resource constitutes a **methodological research instrument**. It does not include empirical data.

2. Theoretical grounding

The coding scheme integrates three complementary theoretical perspectives:

1. **Structural approaches to definition**

Following Trimble (1985), definitions are categorised according to their degree of structural explicitness, distinguishing between canonical and non-canonical definitional forms.

2. **Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL)**

Drawing on Halliday and Matthiessen (2014), the scheme analyses definitions as identifying clauses and captures finer-grained semantic choices through different types of specifying features (differentia) and clause expansions.

3. **Cognitive Discourse Functions (CDFs)**

The scheme aligns with the Cognitive Discourse Functions framework (Dalton-Puffer, 2016), in which defining is treated as a core academic function that may incorporate other discourse functions (e.g. classifying, describing) as components.

3. Unit of analysis

The unit of analysis is an **instance of definition**, defined as a clause or group of clauses that performs the communicative function of specifying the meaning of a disciplinary term.

A single instance may include:

- one or more specifying features (differentia)
- optional expansions that elaborate, extend, or enhance the definition

Multiple codes may be assigned within a single definitional instance.

4. Definition types (structural level)

Definitions are coded according to their structural composition, following Trimble (1985):

Definition type	Operational definition	Illustrative example
Formal (canonical)	Includes explicit class membership (definiens) and at least one specifying feature (differentia).	<i>“A patrician is a social group that held political power and owned large areas of land in Ancient Rome.”</i>

Definition type	Operational definition	Illustrative example
Semi-formal (non-canonical)	Includes specifying features but no explicit class membership.	<i>“Patricians had political rights and were very rich.”</i>
Non-formal	Relies on synonymy, antonymy, or minimal reformulation without specifying features.	<i>“A plebeian is the opposite of a patrician.”</i>

Note. In empirical applications (including Nashaat-Sobhy & Llinares, 2023), non-formal definitions may be grouped analytically with semi-formal definitions due to low frequency.

5. Specifying features (differentia)

Specifying features describe how the definiendum is characterised. Categories are adapted from Halliday and Matthiessen (2014).

Category	Description	Illustrative example
Class	Assigns class membership or functions as a hypernym.	<i>“Patricians were the aristocracy of Rome.”</i>
Quality	Attributes properties or qualities.	<i>“The patricians were rich people.”</i>
Possession	Attributes ownership, rights, or resources.	<i>“Plebeians had some civil rights.”</i>
Circumstance	Specifies time, place, manner, cause, or extent.	<i>“Patricians lived in Ancient Rome.”</i>
Report	Identifies actions, events, or processes.	<i>“During this period, Christopher Columbus discovered America.”</i>
Entity	Attributes group membership without identifying function.	<i>“Plebeians were farmers and artisans.”</i>

6. Expansions of definitions

Definitions may include expansions that elaborate, extend, or enhance meaning beyond the identifying clause.

Expansion type	Description	Illustrative example
Classification	Further categorisation or listing.	<i>“There were three main social groups: patricians, plebeians, and slaves.”</i>
Exemplification	Provision of examples.	<i>“Plebeians were people like peasants and workers.”</i>
Circumstance	Additional contextual information.	<i>“Because they were the richest families in Rome...”</i>
Clarification	Reformulation for greater precision.	<i>“This means that they controlled political decisions.”</i>
Extension	Additional clauses not explicitly marked.	<i>“They were very powerful. They controlled the Senate.”</i>
Explication	Explanation of newly introduced terms.	<i>(Rare in history; more common in science/technology contexts.)</i>

Note. Examples are adapted from student writing analysed in Nashaat-Sobhy & Llinares (2023) and are provided solely for methodological illustration.

7. Coding procedure (Methods-appendix style)

1. Identify all definitional instances in the dataset.
2. Determine whether each instance constitutes a definition.
3. Assign a definition type (formal / semi-formal / non-formal).
4. Code all applicable specifying features (differentia).
5. Code any expansions associated with the definition.
6. Allow multiple codes within a single definitional instance.
7. Resolve coding decisions through discussion and full consensus.

This procedure prioritises **analytic transparency and replicability** rather than quantification per se.

10. Relationship to the original study

This coding scheme was developed and empirically applied in:

Nashaat-Sobhy, N., & Llinares, A. (2023). *CLIL students' definitions of historical terms*. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 26(3), 331–344. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2020.1798868>

The present document extracts, systematises, and makes explicit the **methodological instrument** used in that study. No empirical results are reproduced.

References

Dalton-Puffer, C. (2016). *Cognitive discourse functions: Specifying an integrative interdisciplinary construct*.

Halliday, M. A. K., & Matthiessen, C. (2014). *Halliday's Introduction to Functional Grammar* (4th ed.).

Trimble, L. (1985). *English for Science and Technology: A Discourse Approach*.

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